

Weisgerber-Pohlman Project, Williams County (41.42940, -84.39900)

Since construction in 2022, the primary known nutrient benefit of the Weisgerber-Pohlman Project has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing approximately 0.1 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. Dry conditions in 2024 limited the nutrient filtration opportunity and overall wetland function of the Project, as well as the duration of standing water held in its vernal pools. The capacity of soils at the Project to sorb phosphate remained similar across years, indicating a consistent potential for soils to trap and hold phosphorus when water/nutrient inputs are present.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 70 acres of restored wetland, consisting of five isolated depressional pools and one large floodplain wetland on the north side of the site. The floodplain wetland receives water from the Tiffin River during high flow events, while the isolated depressional pools only receive surface water runoff. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which the Tiffin River floods its bank delivering water to the floodplain wetland.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmland Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
7 acres	0.1 lbs	10 ± 5 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar primarily isolated wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.